

Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and Learning Interest of Grade Six Learners in Araling Panlipunan

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Abstract. This study determined domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers that significantly influence learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. This study used the descriptive correlational design quantitative research design. The respondents of this study were composed of 145 students in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur using the slovin's formula. The data analysis utilized the mean, pearson r and regression analysis. The findings disclosed that level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues was sometimes manifested. Moreover, learning interest of Grade 6 learners in terms of emotion value, knowledge, and engagement was sometimes manifested. It was found out that there was a moderate positive relationship between the Perceived Engagement of Intermediate teachers and Learning Interest of Grade 6 Learners. It revealed further that while certain aspects of perceived engagement are important, Social Engagement with Colleagues stands out as the most influential factor in shaping Grade 6 learners' learning interest. Based on the findings, the teachers should significantly boost students' motivation and interest in learning, while fostering professional collaboration will improve instructional effectiveness and overall classroom experiences.

KEY WORDS

1. Perceived engagement 2. learning interest 3. learners

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1. Introduction

Academic institutions across global, national, and local contexts face many challenges regarding teachers' engagement and impact on student interest in the learning process amidst the current fast-changing, modernized, and digitized world. Studies show that primary learners today barely display learning interest, as shown in their disengagement from schoolwork, increased absences and tardiness rates, easily distracted, failure to participate during class discus-

sions, excessive use of mobile devices amidst class hours, and inappropriate behavior inside the class, among others. Ensuring that teachers' engagement positively impacts learning interest is critically significant for effective learning outcomes.

Similarly, in Mindanao, teachers are looking for possible solutions to solve the low engagement levels among students through innovative teaching tools to address traditional challenges.

However, they find it challenging to attain and maintain elevated levels of student engagement because of the heterogeneous cultural and linguistic situation (Hatmanto et al., 2024).

The researcher was prompted to undertake this study due to escalating concerns regarding the current educational difficulties in Padada District, Davao Del Sur Division, where a disparity between teacher engagement and student interest has been noted, especially in the Araling Panlipunan subject. Although teacher engagement is crucial in creating a dynamic and stimulating classroom atmosphere, its immediate effect on the learning interests of Grade 6 students remains ambiguous. A lack of clarity regarding this link may result in missed opportunities to enhance student learning experiences. This study focuses on three key institutions—Padada Central Elementary School, Padada South Elementary School, and Mariano Sarna Elementary School—to examine the impact of teacher engagement on student interest in social studies, thereby offering insights to enhance teaching methodologies, curriculum design, and overall student engagement.

The study pursued answers to the ensuing objectives: a.) to determine the level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues. b.) to determine the level of learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan in terms of emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement. c.) to determine if there a significant relationship between perceived engagement of intermediate teachers and learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan, and d.) to determine which domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers significantly influence learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypotheses were tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between perceived engagement of intermediate teachers and learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan. b.) None of the domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers significantly influence learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan.

The results and implications of this study were valuable to various stakeholders. For the Department of Education, the findings offered insights into the effectiveness of current teaching methods and supported policy development to enhance teacher training and learning environments. School heads gained a better understanding of how teacher engagement influences student interest, allowing them to implement strategies that promote professional development and a positive school culture. Teachers benefited by learning how their engagement affects student enthusiasm, enabling them to refine their instructional approaches for greater impact. Learners, particularly grade six students, experienced improved motivation and academic performance as a result of more engaging teaching practices. Lastly, future researchers found the study a useful foundation for further exploration into the dynamics between teacher engagement and student interest, contributing to ongoing advancements in education.

Figure 1 illustrated the conceptual framework encompassing the study's variables. The independent variable was perceived engagement of intermediate teachers, defined by cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues. The dependent variable was learning interest of Grade Six learners, encompassing emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study adopted a quantitative methodology, specifically a descriptive-correlational design, to investigate the perceived engagement of intermediate teachers and the learning interests of Grade 6 students in Araling Panlipunan. By integrating systematic observation with relational analysis, this approach offered a comprehensive understanding of real-world classroom dynamics without manipulating variables, thus identifying patterns and trends rather than establishing causality (Creswell Creswell, 2023). The descriptive component assessed the level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of cognitive, emotional, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues, while also assessing the level of learning interest of Grade Six learners in terms of emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement (McCombes, 2023). Concurrently, the correlational aspect examined the strength of the relationship between teacher engagement and student interest (Cherry, 2023). This non-experimental design provided empirical evi-

dence that can inform strategies to improve engagement and enhance the learning experience in Araling Panlipunan.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—This study strictly followed ethical research standards to protect Grade 6 participants from Padada District, Davao del Sur Division, ensuring informed parental and student consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. With significant social value, the research examined how teacher engagement influences students’ interest in Araling Panlipunan, aiming to enhance teaching strategies and student learning experiences. The researcher maintained objectivity by avoiding conflicts of interest, securing appropriate facilities, and upholding justice, privacy, and transparency. Ethical safeguards were applied throughout, including careful survey design, secure data handling, and respectful treatment of all participants, ensuring both integrity and impact of the study.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study was conducted in three randomly selected elementary schools—Padada Central, Padada

South, and Mariano Saroná—in Padada District, Davao del Sur, chosen from a total of 12 schools using the online tool “Wheel of Names” to ensure fair selection. The respondents were Grade 6 students in Araling Panlipunan, with a total population of 228 students across the three schools. Using Slovin’s formula with a 0.05 margin of error, a sample size of 145 was determined, and proportional allocation was used to assign 86 respondents from Padada Central, 35 from Padada South, and 24 from Mariano Saroná. Random selection of participants within each school was also done using the Wheel of Names, ensuring equal opportunity for participation. Only students actively enrolled in Araling Panlipunan and with parental consent were included, promoting consistency in curriculum exposure and ensuring valid, comparable data across all three institutions.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—This study followed a systematic process to ensure the credibility and accuracy of its data and results. It began with securing formal permission from institutional authorities, including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges and the Division Superintendent, followed by issuing approval letters to school administrators and teachers. The research instrument underwent rigorous content validation by educational experts, who assessed its clarity and relevance, leading to necessary refine-

2.6. Data Analysis—To ensure a comprehensive analysis, the study used the mean to assess the levels of teacher engagement and student interest in Araling Panlipunan. Meanwhile,

2.4. Research Instrument—This study utilized two adapted questionnaires: the Engaged Teachers Scale (ETS) by Klassen et al. (2013), and the Academic Interest Scale for Adolescents (AISA) based on Hidi and Renninger’s (2020) four-phase interest development model. The ETS measures teacher engagement across cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions, with a notable emphasis on social engagement with students and colleagues. The AISA, designed to assess academic interest within the education system, demonstrated strong psychometric properties, including a stable four-factor structure (emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement), high reliability, and consistency across demographics, making it a valuable instrument for evaluating student interest across subjects and contexts.

A pilot test was then conducted with 30 non-participant learners to confirm the questionnaire’s reliability under study conditions. The validated questionnaire was administered in person to encourage thoughtful responses, and completed forms were immediately retrieved and reviewed to ensure completeness. Finally, data analysis was performed using SPSS, employing statistical techniques to explore the relationship between teacher engagement and learner interest, thus reinforcing the study’s validity and adherence to ethical research standards.

Pearson r was applied to identify significant correlations, while multiple linear regression determined which aspects of teacher engagement most strongly influenced students’ learning interests.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter delineated the results and discussion of the research. The discussion commenced with a descriptive analysis of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers. Meanwhile, the

next part discussed the learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan, followed by a discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The final presentation emphasized the domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers that significantly influence learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan.

3.1. *Level of Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers*—Table 1 presented a summary of the level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers. These were assessed in terms of cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues. The mean scores for each indicator were the following: Cognitive Engagement (3.05) was characterized as moderate. Emotional Engagement (2.75) was characterized as moderate. Social Engagement with Students (2.92) was characterized as moderate. Social Engagement with Colleagues (3.04) was characterized as moderate.

Table 1. Level of Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Cognitive Engagement	3.05	Moderate
2	Emotional Engagement	2.75	Moderate
3	Social Engagement with Students	2.92	Moderate
4	Social Engagement with Colleagues	3.04	Moderate
Overall		2.94	Moderate

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High

The findings indicated an overall mean rating of (2.94), which was characterized as moderate, this also means that the level of the perceived engagement of intermediate teachers was sometimes manifested. Of the indicators, Cognitive Engagement received the greatest mean rating of (3.04), characterized as moderate, while Emotional Engagement recorded the lowest mean rating of (2.75), also classified as moderate.

3.2. *Level of Learning Interest of Grade 6 Learners*—Table 2 presented a summary of the level of learning interest of Grade 6 learners. These were assessed in terms of emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement. The mean scores

for each indicator were the following: Emotion (3.24) was characterized as moderate. Value (3.24) was characterized as moderate. Knowledge (3.32) was characterized as moderate. Engagement (3.35) was characterized as moderate. The findings indicated an overall mean rating of (3.29), which was characterized as moderate. This suggested that the learning interest of Grade 6 learners was sometimes manifested in schools. Of the indicators, Engagement received the greatest mean rating of 3.35, characterized as moderate, while Emotion and Value recorded the lowest mean rating of (3.24), also classified as moderate.

Table 2. Level of Learning Interest of Grade Six Learners

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Emotion	3.24	Moderate
2	Value	3.24	Moderate
3	Knowledge	3.32	Moderate
4	Engagement	3.35	Moderate
Overall		3.29	Moderate

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and Learning Interest of Grade Six Learners*—Table 3 flaunted the data on the significant relationship between Perceived Engagement of intermediate teachers and Learning Interest of Grade 6 Learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was applied for the two (2) variables on their significant relationship. The results revealed a computed r-value of 0.31 and a p-value of 0.004, which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a moderate positive linear relationship between the Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and the Learning Interest of the Grade 6 Learners. Given that the p-value is below the significance threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that there is

a statistically significant relationship between these two variables, although the correlation is relatively weak.

Furthermore, the computed r-value of 0.31 denotes a moderate correlation between the two variables, with the hypothesis on a significant relationship being tested. Despite the weak correlation, the p-value of 0.004, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, suggests that the relationship is statistically significant. Clearly, the findings infer a significant relationship between the Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and the Learning Interest of Grade 6 Learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. Consequently, it is anticipated that improving teachers’ perceived engagement will enhance students’ learning interest in a diverse cultural classroom environment, thereby positively influencing the overall classroom learning atmosphere.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and Learning Interest of the Grade 6 Learners

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Perceived Engage- ment (x)	0.31	.004	Reject Ho
Learning Interest (y)			

3.4. *Domains of Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers that Significantly Influence Learning Interest of Grade Six learner-*s—Table 4 illustrates the regression test among

the domains of Perceived Engagement—namely Cognitive Engagement, Emotional Engagement, Social Engagement with Students, and Social Engagement with Colleagues—and their influ-

ence on the Learning Interest of Grade 6 learners. The overall model yielded an R-value of 0.31 with a p-value of 0.004, indicating a moderate positive correlation between the two variables. This suggests that the domains of perceived engagement collectively have a statistically significant relationship with students' learning interest. The hypothesis testing confirms the significance of this relationship, as all domains were found to significantly influence learning interest, with p-values well below the 0.05 level of significance.

The findings indicate a moderate but statistically significant relationship between the

perceived engagement of intermediate teachers and the learning interest of Grade 6 learners. The analysis shows an F-value of 68.844 with a p-value of 0.004, indicating a statistically significant model fit. Additionally, the R² value of 0.0961 suggests that approximately 9.61 percent of the variance in learning interest of Grade 6 learners is explained by the four domains of perceived engagement (Cognitive, Emotional, Social Engagement with Students, and Social Engagement with Colleagues). The remaining variance in learning interest can be attributed to factors not accounted for by the domains under study.

Table 4. **Domains of Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers that Significantly Influence Learning Interest of Grade Six Learners**

Perceived Engagement of Intermediate Teachers	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision @=0.05
Constant	2.219	0.270		8.232	.000	
Cognitive Engagement	-0.057	0.058	-0.105	-0.978	.331	Accept H ₀
Emotional Engagement	0.045	0.057	0.076	0.778	.439	Accept H ₀
Social Engagement with Students	0.093	0.062	0.159	1.489	.140	Accept H ₀
Social Engagement with Colleagues	0.265	0.048	0.514	5.489	.000	Reject H ₀

Dependent Variable: Learning Interest of Grade Six Learners
R = 0.31, R² = 0.0961, F-ratio = 6.844, p-value = .004

The regression coefficients indicate that the domains of perceived engagement have varying degrees of influence on the learning interest of Grade 6 learners. While Social Engagement with Colleagues demonstrates the most significant impact, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.265 and a p-value of 0.000, the null hypothesis is rejected for this domain. This suggests that teachers' social engagement with colleagues has a substantial positive effect on students' learning interest.

However, Cognitive Engagement (= -0.057, p-value = 0.331), Emotional Engagement (=

0.045, p-value = 0.439), and Social Engagement with Students (= 0.093, p-value = 0.140) did not show statistically significant influence with students' learning interest, as their p-values exceed the significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted for these domains. Overall, the findings suggest that while certain aspects of perceived engagement are important, Social Engagement with Colleagues stands out as the most influential factor in shaping Grade 6 learners' learning interest.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers, specifically: cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues and to determine the level of the learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan encompassed: emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement, followed by the discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation ends with the domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers that significantly influence learning interest of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—On the level of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, social engagement with students, and social engagement with colleagues revealed that educators exhibit a consistently moderate degree of teaching involvement across cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions. Among these, social involvement with colleagues appeared as the most significant, indicating that teachers prioritize establishing robust connections with their co-workers. Although emotional engagement obtained the lowest average rating, it yet indicates a substantial degree of connection and collaboration. The results underscore the teachers' dedication to their profession, their passion for instruction, and their commitment to cultivating significant relationships inside the classroom and the school community.

On the level of learning interest of the learners in terms of emotion, value, knowledge, and engagement: The findings suggest that Grade 6 learners demonstrate a consistently moderate level of interest in learning Araling Panlipunan. Among the different dimensions of learning interest, the perceived engagement of the subject ranked the highest, indicating that students recognize its significance in their personal growth and future development. While emotional interest and value had the lowest rating, it still remained moderate, reflecting a positive attitude toward the subject.

Clearly, the findings inferred a moderate sig-

nificant relationship between the Perceived Engagement of Intermediate teachers and Learning Interest of Grade 6 Learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. Consequently, it is anticipated that improving teachers' perceived engagement will enhance students' learning interest in a diverse cultural classroom environment, thereby positively influencing the overall classroom learning atmosphere.

to deepen understanding.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the regression analysis, the domains of perceived engagement of intermediate teachers—namely, Cognitive Engagement, Emotional Engagement, Social Engagement with Students, and Social Engagement with Colleagues—were tested for their influence on the learning interest of Grade 6 learners. The analysis reveals that while certain aspects of perceived engagement are important, Social Engagement with Colleagues stands out as the most influential factor in shaping Grade 6 learners' learning interest.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings, it is recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) enhance teacher engagement through strengthened policies, such as Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions and the Modified Program for Rewards and Incentives for Service Excellence (MPRE), to support cognitive, emotional, and social involvement. School heads should foster a collaborative school culture through mentorship, professional development, and shared decision-

making to deepen peer connections and improve morale. Teachers are encouraged to continuously refine their instructional methods and engage in professional collaboration to enrich classroom experiences and student motivation. Students should actively participate in learning by applying lessons meaningfully and building strong relationships with peers and teachers. Future research should investigate additional factors—like teacher well-being and classroom environment—that influence engagement and learning, using varied contexts and long-term studies

5. References

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